

THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT OF CSR INITIATED LEATHER-BASED INDUSTRIES DURING COVID 19 PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT

The leather industry is one of the oldest traditional industries. It makes a significant contribution towards economic growth, balanced regional development, employment generation and overall poverty reduction in the field of leather and allied product manufacturing. The dramatic spread of Covid-19 has threatened human lives, disrupted livelihoods, and affected trade, economy, and businesses across the globe. This pandemic situation is an alarming humanitarian crisis that seeks intensive care and support from the public's health, livelihood, employment, and income of citizens remains questionable. So, companies start to engage in CSR activities in order to respond to a Corporate Governance towards Philanthropic activities during the Covid-19 Pandemic. While taking into consideration the effects of CSR, it is vigorously affected both companies and consumers. This research paper mainly concentrates on the impact of the Socio-Economic condition of Leather-based Industries in Vellore district, Tamil Nadu. This study was conducted using a qualitative approach and data analysis techniques using descriptive statistics. The results of the study found that the spread of Covid-19 had a major economic and social impact on the employees working in leather-based industries. This research attempts to explore the socio-economic impact of CSR-initiated leather-based industries during the Covid-19 pandemic. Profoundly, some positive effects can be seen in terms of improved air quality, water quality, wildlife but the sustainability of such impact is conditional upon post-Covid and people's habits and future policies related to the environment.

Keywords: *Socio-Economic Conditions, CSR Initiated Leather Based Industries, Covid 19 Pandemic.*

INTRODUCTION

The Leather manufacturing sector plays a vital role in the development of our country. It is the major contributor to GDP and the employment-intensive sector, providing jobs to about 2.5 million people, mostly from the weaker sections of the society. This sector has been recognized as an engine for vibrant growth and the creator of the nation's wealth. This sector is working the following segments are given below:

- a. Tanning sector
- b. Footwear

- c. Leather Garments
- d. Leather Goods & Accessories Sector including Saddlery & harness.

The Covid-19 pandemic outbreak is declared internationally as a global health emergency suggested by the World Health Organization (WHO). According to the IMF, this will suggestively reduce world economic activity due to the pandemic outbreak. The Socio-Economic Impact of Covid-19 on Leather Sector to highlight that the spread of Covid-19 pandemic not only affected the Leather Based Industry production chain but also other production chains, like Textile Industries and Automobile industries production chains, etc., These impacts particularly influence the Leather manufacturing chain and make the price of Leather products in the market increasingly falling. It has been going to be affected critically by demand-supply disruptions and the global value supply chain.

According to the Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE), in India, more than 122 million people lost their jobs in April 2020, out of them largely were the wage-laborers and small traders. CSR points out the benefits of the following aspects such as social responsibility, community development, corporate citizenship, and community relations to develop the Corporate Image, brand positioning, enhances the market share, increase sales and ability to strengthens the positive socio-economic condition for Stakeholders. This Research paper acquires the initiative to document the impact of the Covid 19 pandemic on helpless labour communities on Leather Manufacturing sectors through a rapid assessment. Leather Industry and Tannery Workers in the leather sector are a part of the series of research to understand the impact of Covid-19 on the leather industry in the Northern District-Vellore region in Tamil Nadu.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The literature of review aims to find the research gap and adopt the essential conceptual and research papers on the socio-economic conditions of CSR-initiated Leather Based Industries. The researcher attempted to carry out the various researchers' ideology and their analysis on the review was examined in chronological order in this chapter.

Alin Stancu, Georgiana Florentina Grigore and Mihai Ioan Rosca (2011) have analysed the impact of Corporate Social Responsibility on Employees. This paper focuses upon the issues concerning sustainable development that affected both Companies and Consumers. The company starts the CSR activity engage in order to respond to the external demand taking into consideration of the positive effects of CSR. They concluded this study to acquire a better understanding of the employees perceived the CSR activity. Most of the employees are aware of the CSR activities of their employer.

Sonia Wazed (2021) has reviewed the impact of the Covid-19 Recession on Leather and Shoe Workers. This study presents the concept of Leather and Shoe Industry in the India-Kanpur cluster

and, they reported the impact of wages, changes in household income, reduction in food consumption, High-interest Debt, Situation on Resuming work, Precautionary measures at the workplace, Employment Status, Situation of those Laid-off and immediate needs. They concluded this study clearly indicates how inequities play a role in the labour and job market in the Leather Industry and they found the important gap that needs to be filled in order to ensure that people have access to nutritional support and security in times of crisis of self as well as for families.

G.Yoganandham, Jayendra P. Sankar and R. Kalaichelvi (2020) have examined the Socio-Economic Impact on Selected Rural areas Katpadi Taluk in Vellore District. This study reveals the socio-economic conditions of social workers and the general public. Also, there need for support from the financial system and welfare in people's quality of life. They concluded this study the severity of the Covid-19 pandemic has been continuous by the World Health Organization to prevent and restricting disease. Complete lockdown is of great importance for preventive measures to control the virus's spread but, it will create serious economic problems. So, it is a need of an hour to have long-term health care, hospital management plans, financial services, and Governments for the next pandemic.

Dinesh Dhamodhar Mathevan Pillai and et al., (2020) have exposed the impact of socio-economic conditions on the Covid-19 Pandemic. This study reveals the Global and Indian Scenario of the Covid-19 pandemic, and they examined the primary health care guidelines for Corona Virus disease (Covid-19) from the WHO and Indian Ministry of Health and Family Directorate General of Health Services. They concluded this study to monitor the periodic cost-benefit analysis of preventive measures to maintain an economically sustainable solution to prevent the disease.

Rasul G and et al., (2021) have analysed the Socio-Economic implications of the Covid-19 Pandemic in South Asia. This study examined the social risks and growing challenges facing threatened human lives their disrupted livelihoods, and affected trade and economy. They also find the Impact of Migration and Remittance, Increasing risks of Macroeconomic instability, inadequate social security coverage's and shocks in Agriculture and Food security. They concluded this study posed a huge risk and severely impacted the socio-economic conditions and livelihood of people in South Asia. Due to this pandemic, everybody must learn and plan to improve the saving habits of the poor and providing access to banking services would, for instance, provide safety nets during times of crisis.

Sarah Stawiski, Jennifer J. Deal, William Gentry and Simon Rweyongoza (2011) have examined the Corporate Social Responsibility towards Employees Perception. This study finds the relationship between perceived corporate citizenship and commitment, Perceived CSR by Organizational Level, and Leveraging CSR initiatives. They concluded this study reveals the enormous potential to affect their communities and environment by contributing to CSR initiatives, and it should be noted that a

miraculous improvement in retention rates is not likely to be one of them. The CSR will increase in years to reach as people become highly interested in the social and environmental effects of corporations.

Neeraj Kumar (2016) has analysed the role of Leather Industries in the development of our Economy. This study exposed the Leather Industry makes a significant contribution towards economic growth, employment generation and overall poverty reduction, and balanced regional development in the field of Leather products manufacturing. They concluded this study in the various segments of leather industries that play a vital role in the development of our economy. It has been found to yield significant economic benefits in a wide range of nations, specifically reached in its development through other industries' efforts to generate a business in the high technology helps to become a prior competitor in the world economy.

Surui, Doppy Roy Nendissa, and et al., (2020) have analysed the empirical study on the Socio-economic impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on the supply of chicken meat. This study analysed the major impact on all sectors of life, especially health and economy, including the supply chain of Chicken meat. They concluded this study found that the spread of the Covid-19 pandemic, the supply chain system is disrupted due to obstruction by the distribution system. This Covid-19 pandemic can be momentum for conventional to make changes to more modern marketing strategies still comply with government policies to carry out social and physical distancing.

Maria Nicola and et al., (2020) have reviewed the Socio-economic implications of the coronavirus pandemic. This study reveals the sparked fears of impending economic crisis and recession. They found the Socio-economic impact on Primary Sectors like Agriculture, Petroleum & oil, Secondary Sectors like Manufacturing Industry, and Tertiary Sectors like Education, Finance Industry, Healthcare and pharmaceutical Industry, and Hospitality, tourism, and aviation, etc., Finally, they concluded this study with fears of recession and financial collapse in socio-economic development including sector by sector plans. It was prudent that government and financial institutions constantly re-assess and re-evaluate the state of play and ensure that the promise is truly delivered.

Ana Maria Autran Gomez and Luciano A.Favorito (2020) have examined the social, economic and sanitary impact of the Covid-19 pandemic. This study focuses on the Covid-19 Pandemic represents sanitary, social, and economic challenges at a global level. Most countries have faced a shortage of resources like lack of medical equipment, exhaustion with burnout, infections of health care workers, etc. They concluded this study the effort and valuable contribution, hoping that this crisis is going through will allow to grow as people and professionals. "Every crisis has a solution and a learning process."

In this part, the researcher has given an idea about the meaning of CSR and its impact according to the views of various authors in previous studies. Many authors have expressed that the companies are also

managing the CSR practices during the Covid-19 pandemic period. But they are facing a lot of challenges during the Covid-19 pandemic period. Hence, this study focuses on the CSR practices of Leather-based industries during the Covid-19 pandemic period.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The design of the study is a descriptive and diagnostic study, based on both primary and secondary data. The study contemplates the impact of Socio-Economic conditions of employers and employees in Leather Based Industries during the Covid-19 pandemic in the selected rural areas in the Vellore district of Tamil Nadu.

Primary Data:

Predetermined and well-structured interview schedules and focus group discussions were conducted among employers and employees affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. The interviews scheduled were conducted with the employers and employees using a standardized questionnaire. The interviews were done via physical meetings depending on the accessibility and availability of the employers and employees. In-depth interviews were conducted to capture the stories of employers and employees to better understand how the pandemic has impacted their lives. The data collected from the respondents from Leather Based Industries in Vellore Districts from June 2021 – July 2021, with necessary COVID-19 precautionary protocol made the government (face mask, hand gloves, social distancing, and using hand sanitizers frequently).

Secondary Data:

This secondary source of information is gathered from high indexed journals, published data, data from the Council for leather export, Reports from MSMEs, and Ministry of Commerce and Industry, etc.

THE STUDY COVERS

- Socio-Economic Impact on Employers and Employees conditions during the Covid-19 Pandemic Period.
- Accessibility and Availability of social security benefits, including additional support that the employers and employees were expected to receive from the Government during the Pandemic.
- Occupational health and safety measures and potential protective measures adopted by the employers with respect to the employee's safety in the pandemic period.

SAMPLE SIZE AND DESIGN

There are 55 respondents (50 were employees and 5 were employers) selected from Leather-based Industries in the Vellore Region. Most of the employees were from Vellore and very few were from the neighbours' areas. The employees interviewed with different occupational categories such as Skilled, Un-skilled and Supervisors.

QUESTIONNAIRE DESIGN

The questionnaire was distributed for the purpose to know the Socio-Economic Impact of CSR on Leather-based Industries during the Covid-19 Pandemic. We used the Likert's Scale (1-Strongly Disagree, 2-Disagree, 3 Neutral, 4-Agree, 5-Strongly Agree). The questionnaire contains two aspects (1) – Employer Aspect and (2) – Employees Aspect. And these two important aspects in this study were to define the Socio-Economic Conditions of Employers and Employees in Leather-based Industries in Vellore District.

OBJECTIVES

- To analyse the Socio-Economic conditions of Leather-based Industries.
- To examine the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on Leather-based industries.
- To find the association between demographic variables and the influencing factors socio-economic conditions of Leather-based industries.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

This study is intended to analyse the impact of Employees Socio-Economic conditions of Leather-based industries during the Covid-19 Pandemic.

Table 1.1 Demographic profile of the respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
GENDER			
Male	30	60.0	60.0
Female	20	40.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	
AGE			
18 to 25	13	26.0	26.0
25 to 35	30	60.0	86.0
35 to 50	7	14.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	
QUALIFICATION			
School Education	29	58.0	58.0
College Education	16	32.0	90.0
Others	5	10.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	

DESIGNATION			
Skilled	37	74.0	74.0
Unskilled	13	26.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	
INCOME			
5000-10000	33	66.0	66.0
10001 - 15000	14	28.0	94.0
Above 15000	3	6.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	
EXPERIENCE			
Below 1 Year	13	26.0	26.0
2 – 5 Years	32	64.0	90.0
Above 5 Years	5	10.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	
FAMILY TYPE			
Joint Family	35	70.0	70.0
Nuclear Family	15	30.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	
MARITAL STATUS			
Married	41	82.0	82.0
Unmarried	9	18.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	

The overall demographic profile of the employees participated in the study on Socio-Economic impact of Leather-based Industries during Covid-19 pandemic that majority (60%) of the respondent are Male in the study and majority (60%) of the employees are in the Age Group of 25-35 years, the majority (58%) of the employees have only School Education, 74% of the respondents are Skilled Employees, the majority (64%) of the respondents have 2-5 years of experience, the majority (70%) of the respondents are living in Joint Family and majority 82% of the respondents are Married.

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES AND INFLUENCING FACTORS OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONDITIONS

The Employees of Leather-based Industries are affected socially and economically during the Covid-19 Pandemic period. The demographic variables such as Gender, Age, Qualification, Income and Marital Status are considered as independent variables and the influencing factors such as Livelihood, Covid-19 Restriction, Organisational Effectiveness and Personal and Work life Balance are considered as dependent variables. The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was applied to find the association between independent variables on the dependent variables (influencing factors). The results are reported in Tables 1.2 to 1.6.

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN GENDER AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACTS OF EMPLOYEES

Ho: There is no association between Gender and the influencing factors such as Livelihood, Covid-19 Restriction, Organisational Effectiveness and Personal and Work life Balance.

Table 1.2 ANOVA – Association between Gender and Socio-Economic Impacts

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
LIVELIHOOD	Between Groups	2.613	1	2.613	1.097	.300
	Within Groups	114.367	48	2.383		
	Total	116.980	49			
COVID-19 RESTRICTION	Between Groups	5.333	1	5.333	1.990	.165
	Within Groups	128.667	48	2.681		
	Total	134.000	49			
ORGANISATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS	Between Groups	.480	1	.480	.883	.352
	Within Groups	26.100	48	.544		
	Total	26.580	49			
PERSONAL AND WORK LIFE BALANCE	Between Groups	.083	1	.083	.066	.798
	Within Groups	60.417	48	1.259		
	Total	60.500	49			

It is found from table 1.2 that the influencing factors Livelihood, Covid-19 Restriction, Organisational Effectiveness and Personal and Work Life balance which are statistically insignificant at 5 percent level. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is no association between gender and Livelihood, Covid-19 Restriction, Organisational Effectiveness and Personal and Work Life. It implies that both male and female employees have different views about the Covid-19.

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN AGE AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACTS OF EMPLOYEES

Ho: There is no association between Age and the influencing factors such as Livelihood, Covid-19 Restriction, Organisational Effectiveness and Personal and Work life Balance.

Table 1.3 ANOVA – Association between Age and Socio-Economic Impacts

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
LIVELIHOOD	Between Groups	1.573	2	.787	.320	.727
	Within Groups	115.407	47	2.455		
	Total	116.980	49			
COVID-19 RESTRICTION	Between Groups	9.245	2	4.623	1.742	.186
	Within Groups	124.755	47	2.654		
	Total	134.000	49			

ORGANISATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS	Between Groups	1.056	2	.528	.972	.386
	Within Groups	25.524	47	.543		
	Total	26.580	49			
PERSONAL AND WORK LIFE BALANCE	Between Groups	.020	2	.010	.008	.992
	Within Groups	60.480	47	1.287		
	Total	60.500	49			

It is found from table 1.3 that the influencing factors Livelihood, Covid-19 Restriction, Organisational Effectiveness and Personal and Work Life balance which are statistically insignificant at 5 percent level. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is no association between age and Livelihood, Covid-19 Restriction, Organisational Effectiveness and Personal and Work Life. It implies that the different age group of employees have different views about the Covid-19.

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACTS OF EMPLOYEES

Ho: There is no association between Educational Qualification and the influencing factors such as Livelihood, Covid-19 Restriction, Organisational Effectiveness and Personal and Work life.

Table 1.4 ANOVA – Association between Educational Qualification and Socio-Economic Impacts

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
LIVELIHOOD	Between Groups	19.989	2	9.994	4.843	.012
	Within Groups	96.991	47	2.064		
	Total	116.980	49			
COVID-19 RESTRICTION	Between Groups	29.207	2	14.603	6.550	.003
	Within Groups	104.793	47	2.230		
	Total	134.000	49			
ORGANISATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS	Between Groups	1.194	2	.597	1.106	.339
	Within Groups	25.386	47	.540		
	Total	26.580	49			
PERSONAL AND WORK LIFE BALANCE	Between Groups	4.500	2	2.250	1.888	.163
	Within Groups	56.000	47	1.191		
	Total	60.500	49			

It is found from table 1.4 that the influencing factors Livelihood (F=4.843), (P=0.012) and Covid-19 Restriction (F=4.843), (P=0.012), which are statistically significant at 5 percent level. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a deep association between educational qualification and Livelihood and Covid-19 Restriction. It implies that the different education group of employees have a cautious and positive approach to the Covid-19.

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN INCOME AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACTS OF EMPLOYEES

Ho: There is no association between Income and the influencing factors such as Livelihood, Covid-19 Restriction, Organisational Effectiveness and Personal and Work life Balance.

Table 1.5 ANOVA – Association between Income and Socio-Economic Impacts

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
LIVELIHOOD	Between Groups	29.205	2	14.603	7.819	.001
	Within Groups	87.775	47	1.868		
	Total	116.980	49			
COVID-19 RESTRICTION	Between Groups	27.030	2	13.515	5.938	.005
	Within Groups	106.970	47	2.276		
	Total	134.000	49			
ORGANISATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS	Between Groups	3.273	2	1.636	3.300	.046
	Within Groups	23.307	47	.496		
	Total	26.580	49			
PERSONAL AND WORK LIFE BALANCE	Between Groups	14.006	2	7.003	7.080	.002
	Within Groups	46.494	47	.989		
	Total	60.500	49			

It is found from table 1.5 that the influencing factors Livelihood (F=7.819), (P=0.001) and Covid-19 Restriction (F=5.938), (P=0.005), Organisational Effectiveness (F=3.300), (P=0.046) and Personal and Work life Balance (F=7.080), (P=0.002) which are statistically significant at 5 percent level. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a deep association between Income and all the influencing factors. It implies that the different income group of employees have a positive approach to the Covid-19.

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN MARITAL STATUS AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACTS OF EMPLOYEES

Ho: There is no association between Marital Status and the influencing factors such as Livelihood, Covid-19 Restriction, Organisational Effectiveness and Personal and Work life Balance.

Table 1.6 ANOVA – Association between Marital Status and Socio-Economic Impacts

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
LIVELIHOOD	Between Groups	.644	1	.644	.266	.609
	Within Groups	116.336	48	2.424		
	Total	116.980	49			
COVID-19 RESTRICTION	Between Groups	18.867	1	18.867	7.866	.007
	Within Groups	115.133	48	2.399		
	Total	134.000	49			

ORGANISATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS	Between Groups	.531	1	.531	.979	.327
	Within Groups	26.049	48	.543		
	Total	26.580	49			
PERSONAL AND WORK LIFE BALANCE	Between Groups	8.890	1	8.890	8.268	.006
	Within Groups	51.610	48	1.075		
	Total	60.500	49			

It is found from table 1.6 that the influencing factors Covid-19 Restriction ($F=7.866$, $P=0.007$) and Personal and Work Life balance ($F=8.268$, $P=0.006$) which are statistically significant at 5 percent level. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a deep association between Marital Status and all the influencing factors of Covid-19 Restriction and Personal and Work Life balance. It implies that the married group have a more cautious and vigilant approach than the unmarried group of employees about the Covid-19.

IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON SOCIO-ECONOMIC FACTORS

A parametric t-test has been applied to obtain the overall opinion of the respondents about the impact of covid-19 on socio-economic factors. The following are the statements that are considered by respondents towards the impact of covid-19 on socio-economic factors are given in table 1.7.

Table 1.7 One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
LIVELIHOOD	50	16.0200	1.54510	.21851
COVID-19 RESTRICTION	50	16.8000	1.65369	.23387
ORGANISATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS	50	4.7800	.73651	.10416
PERSONAL AND WORK LIFE BALANCE	50	6.1000	1.11117	.15714

It is found from Table 1.7 that all the mean values are greater than 3 in particular ranging from 4.78 to 16.08 with their respective standard deviation. The data is subjected to a t-test and the results are reported in table 1.8.

Table 1.8 One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
LIVELIHOOD	73.314	49	.000	16.02000	15.5809	16.4591
COVID-19 RESTRICTION	71.836	49	.000	16.80000	16.3300	17.2700
ORGANISATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS	45.892	49	.000	4.78000	4.5707	4.9893
PERSONAL AND WORK LIFE BALANCE	38.818	49	.000	6.10000	5.7842	6.4158

It is analysed from table 1.8 that the t-values ranges from 38.818 to 73.314 are statistically significant at 5% level. Therefore it is concluded that the employee completely agreed that the Leather-based Industries are the factors which considered as strong influencing factors during the Covid-19 situation and also have a positive impact.

FINDINGS & CONCLUSION

- The overall demographic profile of the employees participated in the study on Socio-Economic impact of Leather-based Industries during Covid-19 pandemic that majority (60%) of the respondent are Male in the study and majority (60%) of the employees are in the Age Group of 25-35 years, the majority (58%) of the employees have only School Education, 74% of the respondents are Skilled Employees, the majority (64%) of the respondents have 2-5 years of experience, the majority (70%) of the respondents are living in Joint Family and majority 82% of the respondents are Married.
- It is found that there is no association between gender and Livelihood, Covid-19 Restriction, Organisational Effectiveness and Personal and Work Life. It implies that both male and female employees have different views about the Covid-19.
- It is found there is no association between age and Livelihood, Covid-19 Restriction, Organisational Effectiveness and Personal and Work Life. It implies that the different age group of employees have different views
- It is found that there is a deep association between educational qualification and Livelihood and Covid-19 Restriction. It implies that the different education group of employees have a cautious and positive approach to the Covid-19.
- It is found that there is a deep association between Income and all the influencing factors. It implies that the different income group of employees have a positive approach to the Covid-19.
- It is found that the married group have a more cautious and vigilant approach than the unmarried group of employees about the Covid-19.
- It is concluded that the employ completely agreed that Spiritual employees of Leather-based Industries are the factors which considered as strong influencing factors during the Covid-19 situation and also have a positive impact.

The leather and footwear industry was significantly influenced by the Covid-19 pandemic since March 2020 and lost export requests as much as \$ 1 billion because the business sectors of Europe and the USA (which represent about 70% of the exports) were seriously influenced by the illness and the market was shut down, the exports were essentially influenced during April and May 2020, however, showed recuperation patterns during June to September 2020. In contrast with last year, our export execution was 85% in August 2020 in dollar terms. In September 2020, we had accomplished 0.06 percent positive development in exports. The industry essentially supplies for two seasons to be

specific, the Autumn/Winter and Spring/Summer seasons. Last year Spring/Summer deals in our significant business sectors were altogether influenced because of the pandemic, bringing about tremendous reserve up with purchasers. Thus, our exports during October-December 2020 which are essential for the Spring/Summer 2021 season got influenced and with exports enrolling declining pattern.

The Leather area was searching for a turnaround in exports during 2021, yet the spread of the second rush of Covid-19 pandemic in Europe has represented a significant test for recovery of exports. The spread of the second influx of Covid-19 in Europe has represented a significant test for the recovery of exports. Though India is presently seen by the abroad purchasers as a significant objective for sourcing and speculations and thus we unquestionably expect development in exports once the pandemic circumstance moseys down. The leather and footwear industry is a work escalated area, giving employment to 4.42 million individuals. This is feasibly the biggest area giving employment to ladies, as about 40% of labour forces are ladies. It is assessed that about 0.5 million jobless individuals have been utilized in this area over the most recent five years in the wake of going through preparation under different government plans. Hence, the area has awesome potential for producing extra employment openings in the post-Covid-19 period. In spite of the pandemic, the Council for Leather Exports (CLE) is attempted a multi-pronged forceful and supportive dynamic promoting system to tap the expected accessible in different business sectors.

There are excellent opportunities for new companies in the leather and footwear area, as there are acceptable possibilities for development both on the home-grown front and in exports, post-pandemic. The Mega Leather, Footwear and Accessories Development Cluster (MLFACs) will be coming up in different states like Uttar Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal, Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh and so forth, which will be incorporated creation habitats with fitting and-play model of production lines and normal offices like testing research centres and so on, these MLFACs are a decent stage for new businesses. India is the second-biggest purchaser of footwear on the planet and its leather items and footwear market is assessed to be about \$ 12 billion. In addition, India's yearly export of completed leather items and footwear is about \$ 5 billion. With its inborn qualities of the immense crude material base, customary ability, talented labour and utilization of current innovation, India has set up its own standing as a provider of excellent merchandise. The ILO has developed a number of CSR tools and responses. These include:

- Occupational Safety and Health Tips for Workplaces
- Social Protection Responses to the Covid-19 crisis around the world
- Enterprise survey tool: Assessing the needs of enterprises resulting from Covid-19

The respondents who resumed employment after the easing of lockdown measures experienced various challenges. Most workers' wages were drastically reduced, and many received salaries that were lower than the legal minimum wage. Most respondents said that they had found it very difficult

to commute to work in the absence of company transportation and public transportation. It is also evident that most workers experienced uncertainties with respect to working days, work hours, production targets and overtime after returning to the workplace.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Government departments should improve their communication and outreach strategies in order to promote and properly implement Covid-19 aid schemes.
- Government departments should conduct regular monitoring and inspections to ensure that factories comply with the guidelines issued by the government to prevent the spread of Covid-19 at workplaces.
- The government should ensure that all workers receive wages for the lockdown period. Formal notifications should be issued to industries in this regard.
- The labour department should ensure that factories do not indulge in illegal layoffs and terminations. Corrective action should be taken if companies resort to such practices.

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